

EMP-APAC

Financial Analysis of a Large-scale Hydropower Project in Pakistan with a Focus on Clean Energy Transition and National Priorities

- Imtiaz Hussain
- Applied Systems Analysis Division, Pakistan
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Hydropower project financing, financial analysis, Pakistan electricity sector, feasibility, FINPLAN model application

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Executive Summary

This study evaluated the financial viability of a proposed 4,500 MW hydropower project in Pakistan, with a focus on alternative financing structures and sensitivity to macroeconomic and operational risks. Using the FINPLAN model and sectoral data from Pakistan's National Electric Power Regulatory Authority (NEPRA), Independent System and Market Operator (ISMO), and International Monetary Fund (IMF), two scenarios were compared: (i) full private financing with equity and foreign loans, and (ii) partial government support through a grant covering 20% of the local currency component.

Results show that while both scenarios can deliver attractive returns under favorable conditions, the project's resilience is significantly influenced by electricity pricing, production levels, and inflation. Subsidized tariffs and reduced generation substantially erode net present value (NPV) and internal rate of return (IRR), at times making the project financially unattractive. Similarly, higher Pakistan rupee (Rs) inflation relative to the internationally dominated loan imposes additional financing needs, raising project vulnerability. Government support helps ease capital pressure and enhances resilience but cannot fully shield the project from risks of low tariffs or reduced generation.

Overall, large-scale hydropower remains a crucial option for meeting Pakistan's future electricity demand and policy targets, but its financial sustainability depends on realistic pricing, climate resilience, and stable macroeconomic conditions.

1. Introduction

In developing country like Pakistan, access to reliable and affordable electricity is important for sustaining economic growth and achieving national development objectives. Pakistan's final energy consumption during year 2023-24 is around 43 Million Tons Oil Equivalent (HDIP, 2025). Majority of this demand is supplied by fossil fuels. Electricity accounts for 21.2% of final energy consumption.

Figure 1: Annual final energy consumption

Figure 2: Annual electricity generation

Around 137 Billion kWh of electricity is generated in Pakistan during 2023-24 (NEPRA, 2024) with about half of this electricity coming from fossil fuel power plants. Share of renewables, including hydro, in total electricity generation is around 34%. Growing demand of electricity, along with heavy reliance on imported fossil fuels has created serious challenges. The rising system cost means higher bills for consumers and more financial challenges for the economy, while increased use of fossil fuels has led to environmental degradation and higher carbon emissions. Additionally, reliance on imported fuels exposed the country to global price fluctuations and raises concerns about energy security. To overcome these challenges, there is a clear need to shift towards more reliable, affordable and sustainable energy sources. Developing indigenous resources such as hydropower and renewable energy can help stabilize costs, reduce environmental impacts, and enhance the country's energy security, thereby, supporting long-term growth and sustainability.

The National Electricity Policy 2021 sets a target to generate 60% of country's annual electricity from renewable sources, including hydropower, by 2030 (M/o Energy, 2021) (M/o Energy, 2023). Additionally, to reduce the reliance on imported fuels, the policy also

aims 70% electricity generation from indigenous resources by 2030. According to the projections by Pakistan's Independent System and Market Operator (ISMO), total electricity demand is expected to reach 173 Billion kWh by 2030 (ISMO, 2025), representing an increase of 26% from the current level. Meeting this rising demand whilst also meeting the nationally determined contribution (NDC) targets will require a significant expansion of clean energy sources.

Keeping in view the electricity demand projections and government's priorities of renewable and hydropower generation, there is a strong case for developing large-scale hydropower projects, along with multiple renewable energy initiatives by the year 2030. However, financing capital-intensive power projects in Pakistan presents a significant challenge due to political and policy uncertainty, circular debt, exchange rate risks, limited local financing capacity, and sovereign debt concerns.

1.1. Objective

The objective of this study is to evaluate alternative financing structures and analyse the robustness of the proposed 4500 MW hydropower project against macroeconomic and capacity changes in order to determine the most appropriate option. The study considers the expected returns for stakeholders as well as the creditworthiness of electricity consumers.

2. Methodology

2.1. Modeling Approach

Financial modelling is the task of building an abstract representation of real world financial situation. This work analysed the financial sensitivities of the proposed project using FINPLAN model. FINPLAN is an analytical tool, developed by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), for facilitating the financial analysis of power projects (OU, 2024). It is an accounting model that follows standard business accounting principles for recognizing, measuring and reporting an entity's financial transactions. It can be used to design a financing package of a power project, to evaluate alternative financing options, or to analyse various financing uncertainties associated with a project.

2.2. Data sources

Plant related input parameters required for the FINPLAN model are derived from the hydropower projects data available on the website of NEPRA and reports published by

ISMO. Moreover, the International Monetary Fund's (IMF) database has been consulted for selecting suitable economic and financial input parameters.

2.3. Assumptions

Major plant related parameters of the project are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1: Project description

Plant Type	Hydropower Plant
Plant Size	4500 MW
Construction Period	6 Years
Construction Start Year	2024
First Year of Operation	2030
Plant Life	50 Years
Capital Cost	\$ 4,800 Million (1067 \$/kW)
Annual Capacity Factor	48.7%
Annual Generation	19,200 GWh
Annual O&M Cost	Rs 6,000 Million (0.15 Rs/kW/h)
Depreciation	Declining balance at 15%

Economic and financial parameters used for assessing the sensitivity of the project are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Economic and financial parameters

Economic Parameters	
Inflation of \$	2.2%
Inflation of Pak Rs	5.0%
Exchange Rate	290 Rs/\$
Income Tax	15%*
Discount Rate	12%
Financial Parameters	
Capital Cost	\$ 4,800 Million (1,067 \$/kW)
Foreign Exchange (FE) Component	60% (\$ 2,880 Million)
Local Currency (LC) Component	40% (Rs 547,200 Million)

Source of Financing	
Export Credit	85% of Total FE Investment \$ 2,448 Million
For analysis, a mix of equity and loan has been considered, keeping in view the capacity of the project sponsor to manage equity and volume of loan.	
Terms of Financing	
Export Credit	Interest Rate: 6% Term: 40 Years
Loan	Annual Interest Rate: 2% above \$ inflation Term: 12 Years

* At present, income from electricity generation projects in Pakistan is exempt from taxation (FBR, 2025). However, given the prevailing circumstances and frequent media reports on non-payments of tax by the Independent Power Producers (IPPs), it is reasonable to anticipate that the government may introduce an income tax in the near future. Accordingly, a 15% income tax has been assumed in this case study.

2.4. Scenarios and sensitivity analysis

Two scenarios have been considered for assessing the alternative financing structure of the project. Additionally, the sensitivity of these scenarios have been analysed for three different cases for assessing the impact of sale price variation, reduced production and increased Rs inflation on the viability of the project.

Scenario 1: The project would be entirely financed by the equity from the project owner and foreign exchange (FE) loan from multilateral development banks, keeping the debt equity ratio of around 0.7 during the construction years.

Scenario 2: Government would support of 20% of LC component of the project in the form of grant without the obligation of repayment, which would supplement the debt portion of financing.

Cases for sensitivity analysis:

1. Impact of sale price variation on NPV and IRR of the shareholders
2. Impact of reduced production on NPV and IRR of the shareholders
3. Impact of increase in Rs inflation on the project financing

3. Results

In 2023-24, Pakistan's national average electricity generation tariff was approximately Rs 24/kWh (NEPRA, 2024) with expectations of a downward trend in the coming years driven by measures such as the revision of power purchase agreements (PPAs) with the

Independent Power Producers (IPPs). For this study, a reference sale price of Rs 20/kWh was assumed for the proposed hydropower project, which was then gradually reduced to assess its impact on NPV and IRR from the shareholders' perspective. For scenario 1, around \$1.5 Billion of loan would be required to finance the project in order to keep the financing ratios at suitable levels. Loan requirement for scenario 2 is around \$600 Million. Outcomes of these cases and scenarios are discussed in the following sub-sections.

3.1. Impact of subsidized sale price

Subsidizing the sales price so that it does not increase in line with the inflation rate can severely erode the investors' returns. To assess this impact, three cases were analysed. In the first case, prices are assumed to rise in line with inflation, with no subsidy applied. Second case assumes a partial subsidy, where prices increase at only half the rate of inflation, and the remaining 50% is covered through subsidy. In third case, electricity prices are assumed to be heavily subsidized, rising at just 25% of the inflation rate.

Following paragraphs discusses the impacts and, Table 3 and Table 4 presents the FINPLAN results of different cases for scenario 1 and scenario 2, respectively.

Scenario 1: No Government Support

Case 1: No subsidy, i.e., electricity prices increase in line with inflation:

The IRR of the project reduces from 25.1% to 13.0% as we reduced the sale price from the reference Rs 20/kWh to Rs 8/kWh, showing a fair resilience of the project to the decrease of the electricity price.

Case 2: Partial subsidy, i.e., electricity prices increase at half the rate of inflation:

In this case, the project NPV declines significantly relative to the previous case, potentially undermining the investors' confidence. Also, the margin for decreasing the sales price from the reference value shrinks significantly in this case.

Case 3: High subsidy, i.e., electricity prices increase at 25% of the inflation rate:

In this case, the project returns becomes very low from the investors point of view. Also, the project becomes highly vulnerable, where even a slight reduction in the sale price from the reference level could prevent it from recovering its fixed costs.

Table 3: Impacts of subsidizing sales price for scenario 1

Sales Price (Rs/kWh)	NPV (Billion Rs)			IRR (%)		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
	Sales cost increases in line with inflation	50% subsidized sales price w.r.to inflation	75% subsidized sales price w.r.to inflation	Sales cost increases in line with inflation	50% subsidized sales price w.r.to inflation	75% subsidized sales price w.r.to inflation
20	1,754.5	727.2	452.4	25.1	19.6	17.3
17	1,328.3	458.7	227.0	22.2	16.9	14.8
14	906.2	196.5	10.3	19.3	14.2	12.1
11	492.9	-50.5	-188.4	16.2	11.4	9.4
8	101.8	-265.1	-349.1	12.9	8.4	6.4
5	-234.0	-410.8	-521.0	9.4	4.5	0.0

Scenario 2: With Government Support

Case 1: No subsidy, i.e., electricity prices increase in line with inflation:

In this case, the project indicates healthy returns to shareholders. The resilience to reduction of sales price is also fine as the project remains profitable even after a reduction of electricity price to Rs 8/kWh.

Table 4: Impacts of subsidizing sales price for scenario 2

Sales Price (Rs/kWh)	NPV (Billion Rs)			IRR (%)		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
	Sales cost increase in line with inflation	50% subsidized sales price w.r.t. inflation	75% subsidized sales price w.r.t. inflation	Sales cost increase in line with inflation	50% subsidized sales price w.r.t. inflation	75% subsidized sales price w.r.t. inflation
20	1940.1	912.0	635.8	29.4	23.6	21.1
17	1513.5	639.8	406.2	26.1	20.4	18.0
14	1087.3	371.2	180.3	22.5	17.1	14.8
11	666.0	110.7	-34.4	18.8	13.6	11.4
8	258.5	-126.8	-220.9	14.8	10.0	7.9
5	-105.5	-302.1	-334.0	10.6	5.8	3.3

Case 2: Partial subsidy, i.e., electricity prices increase at half the rate of inflation:

In this case, the project NPV declines relative to the previous case, potentially undermining the investors' confidence. Also, the margin for decreasing the sales price from the reference value shrinks in this case.

Case 3: High subsidy, i.e., electricity prices increase at 25% of the inflation rate:

For this case, project becomes highly vulnerable, and non-attractive for investors. Even a slight reduction in the sale price from the reference level could prevent the project from recovering its fixed costs in this case.

3.2. Impact of reduced production

Hydropower plant's output depends on river inflows, which is vulnerable to climate change, droughts, and seasonal variability. This study explores how reduced generation affects investor returns and project affordability by analysing three cases: (i) a business-as-usual (BAU) case with production at the rated 48.7% capacity factor, (ii) a moderate reduction to 40% capacity factor, and (iii) a severe decline in production to 25% capacity factor reflecting extreme climate or drought conditions.

Table 5 and Table 6 presents the FINPLAN results of different cases.

Scenario 1: No Government Support

Case 1: No reduction in output, i.e., production at rated 48.7% capacity factor:

This is the BAU case of scenario 1, presenting similar results as that in the previous section. Output of the model represents a fair resilience of the project to the decrease of the electricity price.

Case 2: Moderate reduction of output to 40% capacity factor:

In this case, the NPV declines and becomes negative at Rs 8/kWh, depicting that a narrow margin for electricity price reduction is available.

Case 3: Severe reduction in output to 25% capacity factor:

In this case, NPV declines sharply and the project becomes highly vulnerable. The returns in this case are very low and risks so high that a reduction of electricity price to Rs 14/kWh can lead to the failure of the project.

Table 5: Impacts of reduced production for scenario 1

Sales Price (Rs/kWh)	NPV (Billion Rs)			IRR (%)		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
	48.7% Capacity factor	40% Capacity factor	25% Capacity factor	48.7% Capacity factor	40% Capacity factor	25% Capacity factor
20	1754.5	1247.3	394.1	25.1	21.7	15.4
17	1328.3	900.8	193.1	22.2	19.2	13.7
14	906.2	560.3	3.2	19.3	16.7	12.0
11	492.9	232.8	-169.3	16.2	14.1	10.2
8	101.8	-68.5	-315.4	12.9	11.3	8.1
5	-234.0	-315.4	-697.3	9.4	8.1	0.0

Scenario 2: With Government Support

Case 1: No reduction in output, i.e., production at rated 48.7% capacity factor:

This is the BAU case of scenario 2. Output of the model presents healthy returns to the investors and fair resilience of the project to the decrease of the electricity price.

Case 2: Moderate reduction of output to 40% capacity factor:

In this case, the NPV declines to a very low value at the sales price of Rs 8/kWh, depicting that a margin for electricity price reduction is still available.

Case 3: Severe reduction in output to 25% capacity factor:

In this case, NPV falls steeply, diminishing the project's appeal to investors.

Table 6: Impacts of reduced production for scenario 2

Sales Price (Rs/kWh)	NPV (Billion Rs)			IRR (%)		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
	48.7% Capacity factor	40% Capacity factor	25% Capacity factor	48.7% Capacity factor	40% Capacity factor	25% Capacity factor
20	1940.1	1431.7	564.2	29.4	25.5	17.8
17	1513.5	1081.8	354.7	26.1	22.5	15.8
14	1087.3	735.3	153.1	22.5	19.4	13.7
11	666.0	396.2	-33.8	18.8	16.2	11.6
8	258.5	76.2	-195.0	14.8	12.9	9.2
5	-105.5	-195.0	-323.8	10.6	9.2	0.0

3.3. Impact of increased inflation

Increased inflation of Pakistan Rs would have severe consequences on the financing of the project, as it will require bridging the additional finance requirement from the stand-by facility which is a very expensive financing option having a spread of 10% above inflation. In this case, it is assumed that inflation of Pakistan Rs increase from 5% to 7% and the corresponding impact on the additional capital requirement is analysed for the two scenarios. For the first scenario, an additional Rs 115 Billion would be required, whereas, for the second case, around Rs 85 Billion of stand-by facility would be required. Accumulation of stand-by facility over the six years of construction period in the two scenarios is shown in the Figure 3.

Figure 3: Accumulated stand-by facility for both scenarios if Rs inflation increased from 5% to 7%

4. Discussion

The analysis highlights several important insights for policymakers, investors, and energy planners, which are discussed in the following paragraphs.

4.1. Pricing and Tariff Policy

Sustainable electricity pricing is important to project viability. High subsidies significantly reduce investor returns. Without cost-reflective tariffs or alternative compensation mechanisms, large-scale hydropower projects may struggle to attract financing.

4.2. Climate and Seasonal Risk

Output of hydropower plant depends on river inflows, which is vulnerable to droughts, climate change impacts, and seasonal fluctuations. Severe reductions in capacity factor hugely effects project economics. This emphasizes the need for integrating hydrological risk assessments, climate adaptation and mitigation strategies in the planning process.

4.3. Macroeconomic Risks

Exchange rate volatility and inflation pressures are critical risks. The results show that even a modest increase in Rs inflation requires substantial additional financing, often through expensive stand-by facilities. This underscores the importance of stable macroeconomic policies and access to concessional finance.

4.4 Role of Government Support

While government support in the form of grants improves the financing structure and enhances resilience, it cannot fully offset the risks related to production shortfalls or tariff

suppression. Public-private partnerships (PPP), long-term PPAs, and risk-sharing mechanisms with multilateral institutions may provide more robust solutions.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the proposed 4,500 MW hydropower project can be financially viable but remains highly sensitive to electricity pricing, production levels, and macroeconomic conditions. Under a fully private financing structure, approximately \$1.5 Billion in loans are required, while government support covering 20% of the local currency component reduces the loan requirement to about \$600 Million, thereby improving financial resilience. Results indicate that the project remains profitable and attractive to investors when the electricity sales price is maintained at or above Rs 14-17/kWh, even under moderate production shortfalls. However, with heavy tariff subsidies or severe reductions in output, the NPV turns negative, making the project unattractive despite government support. Furthermore, a rise in Rs inflation could create additional financing through expensive stand-by facilities, further challenging affordability. The study suggests that government support in the range of 5%-15% of project capital costs is generally adequate to sustain investor confidence and keep tariffs affordable, provided that macroeconomic conditions remain stable and production levels are not severely reduced. These findings indicate that while large-scale hydropower can play a pivotal role in meeting Pakistan's target of generating 60% electricity from renewables by 2030, its sustainability depends on government injections of capital, realistic tariff adjustments, and proactive management of climate and macroeconomic risks.

References

FBR, 2025. *Income Tax Ordinance 2001, Amended upto 31 July 2025*. Islamabad: Federal Board of Revenue, Ministry of Finance, Pakistan.

HDIP, 2025. *Pakistan Energy Yearbook 2023-24*. Islamabad: Hydrocarbon Development Institute of Pakistan (HDIP), Petroleum Division, Ministry of Energy, Pakistan.

ISMO, 2025. *Indicative Generation Capacity Expansion Plan 2025-35*. Islamabad: Independent System and Market Operator (ISMO), Pakistan.

M/o Energy, 2021. *National Electricity Policy 2021*. Islamabad: Power Division, Ministry of Energy, Pakistan.

M/o Energy, 2023. *National Electricity Plan 2023-27*. Islamabad: Power Division, Ministry of Energy, Pakistan.

NEPRA, 2024. *State of the Industry Report 2024*. Islamabad: National Electric Power Regulatory Authority (NEPRA), Pakistan.

OU, 2024. *Course: Financial Analysis of Power Projects using the FINPLAN Model, Lecture 5: Credit Optiond and FINPLAN Methodology*. s.l.:Open University, UK.

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